

VOLATILE PARTITIONING DURING LUNAR DIFFERENTIATION: CONSEQUENCES FOR CORE COMPOSITION AND TRANSIENT ATMOSPHERE FORMATION. C. P. Haupt¹ F. M. McCubbin² and F. Gaillard³, ¹ISTO, UMR 7327, Univ Orléans, CNRS, BRGM, OSUC, 45071 Orléans, France, ²Astromaterials Research & Exploration Science Division, NASA Johnson Space Center, NASA Parkway, Houston TX 77058, USA

Introduction: Despite the generally accepted view that the Moon formed in a hot impact scenario, analyses of lunar samples indicate the existence of mantle source regions containing up to 740 ug/g of water [1]. A second line of evidence for a non-dry lunar interior is provided by water ice deposits in permanently shadowed polar regions, which have been suggested to be of endogeneous origin [2]. Numerous studies have constrained the abundances of magmatic volatiles (C, S, and O) in the bulk silicate Moon (BSM), whereas H remains comparatively uncertain [3]. However, the implications of a volatile-bearing BSM for lunar core formation and evolution of a transient atmosphere remain poorly explored.

Method: In this study, we apply a planetary differentiation model that distributes a predefined bulk lunar composition into a metallic core and a silicate mantle reservoir, based on recent experimental and numerical solubility models [e.g., 4]. Remaining volatiles are subsequently degassed into an atmosphere, with speciation calculated using established thermodynamic models [5].

The differentiation model explicitly tracks volatile elements (H, S, C, O) throughout the entirety of differentiating reservoirs, providing an integrated picture of the volatile distribution within the Moon. By benchmarking model outputs against BSM volatile estimates [3] and geophysical constraints [6], we identify the best-fit scenarios and evaluate the consequences of variable bulk lunar H contents across the range inferred from sample analyses.

Results and Implications: Modeling results are consistent with a bulk lunar composition similar to that suggested by O'Neill (1991) containing 9.6 wt% Fe [7]. Following differentiation, the model yields a core comprising 1.7-1.9 wt% of the Moon, dominated by Fe, and a BSM containing ~10.3 wt% FeO. These values are consistent with widely accepted estimates for lunar mantle composition, core composition, and core size.

Volatiles in the lunar core

The modelled lunar core is composed of >98wt% Fe, with minor amounts of light elements (≤ 0.97 wt% S, ≤ 0.1 wt% O, ≤ 0.3 wt% C, and $\leq 5 \cdot 10^{-4}$ wt% H).

Volatiles in the lunar Mantle

The exploratory maximum-H scenario considered here, with up to 200 ug/g H in the bulk Moon – exceeding plausible post-giant impact scenarios – results in no more than ~370 ug/g H₂O in the lunar magma ocean. This value is approximately half of

that proposed for the source regions of the most primitive lunar samples [1].

More realistic bulk lunar H contents (e.g., 10 ug/g bulk Moon, assuming $\geq 90\%$ volatile loss from a bulk silicate Earth-like composition containing ~80 ug/g H [8]) yield BSM water contents of up to ~70 ug/g. This is in excellent agreement with suggested estimates for the BSM [3].

The initial bulk lunar C and S contents required to reproduce the inferred BSM abundances follow the expected depletion trend relative to the bulk silicate Earth, with S being the least depleted [3].

Lunar transient atmosphere and surface ice

Degassing a lunar magma ocean generates a primary atmosphere with total pressures ≥ 1 bar when the initial bulk H content exceeds 10 ug/g. Under these conditions, the atmosphere is CO-dominated; at H contents >10 ug/g, H₂ becomes the dominant species. In all scenarios, H₂O is the third most abundant atmospheric species.

When combined with estimates for volatile release during mare volcanism and water preserved in permanently shadowed regions, our results indicate that retention of only 1-15 % of the initial volatile inventory in the BSM during differentiation is sufficient to account for CO, S, and H₂O required to form these deposits. An additional endogeneous volatile source is therefore not required.

Conclusions: Benchmarking of a planetary differentiation model against compiled geochemical and geophysical constraints supports the formation of the Moon from a bulk silicate Earth-like composition during the giant impact scenario. Best-fit solutions indicate that even a volatile-depleted Moon, retaining only small fractions of volatiles during differentiation, can sustain basaltic magmatism and degas sufficient water to account for ice deposits in permanently shadowed polar regions.

References:

- [1] Saal A. et al. (2008) *Nature*, 454, 192–195.
- [2] Needham D. H. and Kring D. A. (2017) *Earth Planet Sci Lett*, 478, 175-178.
- [3] McCubbin F. M. et al. (2023) *Rev Mineral Geochem*, 89, 729–786.
- [4] Chaudhari A. et al. (2025) *Contrib Mineral Petrol*, 180, 84.
- [5] Gaillard F. et al (2022) *Earth Planet Sci Lett*, 577, 117225.
- [6] Garcia R. F. et al. (2019) *Space Sci Rev*, 215, 50.
- [7] O'Neill H. St. C. (1991) *Geochim Cosmochim Acta*, 55, 1135-1157.
- [8] Grewal D. S. et al. (2024) *Planet Sci J*, 5, 181.